

Chemical Investigation of *Pyrus sikkimensis*

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Pyrus sikkimensis (Fam. Rosacea) is a medium-sized tree growing abundantly in Himalayan region of Khashi and Jaintia Hills.

Several crystalline compounds have been isolated from the different extracts of the plant among which *n*-triacontane, myricyl alcohol, friedelin, β -amyrin and β -sitosterol from petroleum ether (60–80°) extract have been identified. Epifriedelinol was isolated from the chloroform extract of the plant. The cold ethanolic extract furnished a red gummy residue which is under investigation.

Air dried, powdered plant was extracted successively with light petroleum ether (60–80°), chloroform and ethanol (90%).

Thin layer chromatography on silica gel with the light petroleum fraction showed five distinct spots of different R_f and a less intensive spot. Chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina of the product obtained from the light petroleum ether extract, furnished several crystalline fractions when eluted with solvents of increasing polarity.

Solvents	Residue left on evaporation
Petroleum ether (60–80°)	Solid, Fraction I
Petroleum-benzene (9 : 1)	Solid, Fraction II
-do- (8 : 2)	Solid, Fraction III
-do- (7 : 3)	Nil
-do- (6 : 4)	Solid, Fraction IV
-do- (1 : 1)	Nil
Benzene	Fraction V
Benzene-chloroform	Nil

Fraction I, m.p. 66° (ethyl acetate) showed no coloration with tetranitromethane, (Found : C, 85.22; H, 14.70%; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{62}$: C, 85.31%; H, 14.69%). The compound was found identical with *n*-triacontane¹ (mixed m.p. and T.L.C.).

Fraction II, m.p. 85° (ethyl acetate) gave no coloration with tetranitromethane, (Found : C, 82.13%; H, 14.24; Calc. for $C_{30}H_{62}O$: C, 82.22; H, 14.15%). The identity of the compound as myricyl alcohol was established from its direct comparison with an

1. Klobb, *et al.*, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1910, 7, 940.

authentic sample (mixed m.p. and T.L.C.) and the acetyl derivative of the compound (m.p. 68°) with an authentic sample of the acetate of myricyl alcohol (mixed m.p.).

Fraction III, m.p. 255–56° (methanol) responded to Liebermann Burchard test and exhibited no coloration with tetranitromethane showing absence of unsaturation in the molecule. IR : 1710 cm^{-1} indicated six-membered saturated ketone, $[\alpha]_D - 28^\circ$ (CHCl_3). These observations together with direct comparison (mixed m.p., T.L.C. Rf 0.7 using benzene-chloroform as developer) established the identity of the compound with friedelin^{2,3}.

The oxime m.p. 290° (ethyl acetate-benzene) was identical with friedelin-oxime (mixed m.p. and T.L.C.).

Fraction IV, m.p. 195° (benzene) showed positive test for triterpene. The presence of -OH group was evident from the appearance of peak at 3.04 μ in the IR spectrum (Nujol). The identity of the compound as β -amyrin was further established by direct comparison (mixed m.p., rotation $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 86^\circ$ (CHCl_3)) with an authentic sample of β -amyrin. The acetate, m.p. 238–40° was identical with β -amyrin acetate from mixed m.p. (undepressed) and superimposable IR data with an authentic sample of β -amyrin acetate.

Fraction V, m.p. 136° (methanol) was homogeneous towards TLC and responded to Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterols. The acetyl derivative, m.p. 127° (methanol) $[\alpha]_D - 40.5^\circ$ (CHCl_3) was identical with acetate of β -sitosterol.

The chloroform extract on being subjected to chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina yielded a crystalline solid. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 280°. The compound, $[\alpha]_D + 20^\circ$ (CHCl_3) showed peak at 3500 cm^{-1} (OH) in IR spectrum. The identity of the compound as epifriedelinol was established by direct comparison (mixed m.p. and T.L.C.) with an authentic sample of epifriedelinol⁴.

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